

FACEBOOK USAGE ON JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' READING HABITS, ATTITUDES, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 6

Pages: 676-689

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1789

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11114205

Manuscript Accepted: 04-01-2024

Facebook Usage on Junior High School Students' Reading Habits, Attitudes, and Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of Facebook usage on the reading habits, attitudes, and academic performance of 150 secondary students at Pantar National High School, Division of Lanao del Norte, during the School Year 2023-2024. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, statistical tools such as Frequency and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation calculations, Pearson r correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis were utilized for data analysis. Findings revealed distinct patterns in the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading habits. Students expressed a moderate impact on reasons for reading, emphasizing the platform's role in shaping motivations. Reading preferences showed an overall positive impact, highlighting Facebook's influence on content preferences. Distractions during reading reflected a moderate impact, emphasizing the nuanced role of Facebook in concentration. In examining perceived impacts on reading attitudes, students exhibited a modest influence on self-efficacy and motivation to read. However, a notable impact on the perceived importance of reading was observed. Academic performance exhibited a predominantly positive distribution where the majority achieved a "Very Satisfactory" level, and few attained an "Outstanding" performance. It was indicative of a positive academic environment. The ordinal regression revealed that there was no found significant impact of Facebook Usage on their reading habits and the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading attitudes.

Keywords: *facebook usage, academic performance, reading habits, reading attitude, reading preferences*

Introduction

In today's digital age, Facebook has become an integral part of the lives of many individuals, especially the younger generation. While Facebook has various benefits, it has also raised concerns about its impact on reading habits and attitudes among students. Reading is a fundamental skill that is essential for academic success and lifelong learning. However, the prevalence of Facebook use among students has been linked to a decline in their reading habits and attitudes towards reading. Many students spend a significant amount of time on Facebook, such as Facebook, decreasing the time they dedicate to reading. This issue raises concerns about the impact of Facebook on the reading habits and attitudes of secondary school students (Geronimo & Llantero, 2018).

The decline in reading habits and attitudes among secondary school students may have long-term implications on their academic performance and their ability to succeed in higher education. It may also hurt their critical thinking skills and ability to communicate effectively.

Several studies have examined the relationship between Facebook and reading habits and attitudes among students in the Philippines. A study by Atienza et al. (2020) found that Facebook use significantly negatively impacted the reading habits of senior high school students in the Philippines. Another study by Valdez and Bacani (2018) found that Facebook use hurt the reading attitudes of college students in the Philippines.

While some studies have examined the relationship between Facebook and reading habits and attitudes among students in the Philippines, there is still a research gap in understanding how Facebook influences the reading habits and attitudes of secondary school students.

This study aimed to examine the influence of the use of Facebook on the reading habits and attitudes of secondary school students in Pantar National High School, Pantar District, Division of Lanao del Norte, School Year 2023-2024. By understanding these relationships, the study aimed to provide recommendations for educators and parents to help students develop better reading habits and attitudes.

Research Questions

The study aimed to examine the influence of the usage of Facebook on secondary student's reading habits and attitudes and academic performance at Pantar National High School, Division of Lanao del Norte, School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the impact of Facebook usage on student's reading habits in terms of:
 - 1.1 reasons for reading;
 - 1.2 reading preferences; and
 - 1.3 distractions while reading?
2. What is the impact of Facebook usage on student's reading attitudes in terms of:

- 2.1 self-efficacy in reading comprehension;
- 2.2 motivation to read; and
- 2.3 perceived importance of reading?
3. How many hours do the respondents use Facebook?
4. What is the academic performance of the students based on their final ratings for the previous school year?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the impact of Facebook usage on their reading habits?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the impact of Facebook usage on their reading attitudes?
7. Which of the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading habits and the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading attitudes significantly predict the academic performance of students?
8. What action plan can be designed based on the findings?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods used in the study. It discussed the research design, research environment, respondents and sampling procedures, research instruments and their validity, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of the data.

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational research design used in the study at Pantar National High School aimed to explore the influence of Facebook usage on secondary students' reading habits, attitudes, and academic performance during the school year 2022-2023. Descriptive research involved collecting data to characterize the variables under investigation. In this case, the study sought to describe the relationship between Facebook use, reading habits, attitudes, and academic performance among secondary students. Meanwhile, correlational studies typically use statistical methods to analyze data and determine the strength and direction of relationships between variables.

Participants

The respondents of this study were randomly selected from 150 secondary students from Pantar National High School, Pantar District, Division of Lanao del Norte. The randomly selected 150 students were composed of 40 students from Grade 7, 30 students from Grade 8, 40 students from Grade 9, and 40 students from Grade 10.

The random selection of participants was performed to ensure that the sample is representative of the population of Junior High School students in the said school to ensure the ethical considerations of the respondents. Also, informed consent was obtained from the participants before their involvement in the study. The confidentiality of the participants was maintained, and all data collected were treated with the utmost confidentiality and were used for research purposes. The table below presents the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Total Number of Students</i>	<i>No. of Actual Respondents</i>
7	280	40
8	247	30
9	270	40
10	240	40
Total	1037	150

Instruments

The study used the researcher-made questionnaire due to the unavailability of a suitable standardized questionnaire. The instrument was composed of the following sections. Part 1 of the questionnaire comprised the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading habits in terms of reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions while reading. This part of the questionnaire was rated using a four-point Likert scale such as 4 as highly observed, 3 as observed, 2 as rarely observed, and 1 as never observed.

Part 2 of the questionnaire was composed of statements to describe the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading attitudes in terms of self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, and perceived importance of reading. This part of the questionnaire was rated using a four-point Likert scale such as 4 as highly observed, 3 as observed, 2 as rarely observed, and 1 as never observed. Meanwhile, the academic performance of the students was based on their previous performance for the school year 2022-2023.

Since the instrument used was researcher-made, the validation process was ensured. To strengthen the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaires, three (3) panel experts considered checking the appropriateness of the research instrument before the actual gathering of data. This was supported by pilot testing results. The suggestions and comments were the basis for the final research instrument.

A pilot survey involved twenty-five participants at Balo-i National High School in the Lanao Norte district. This would examine the

dependability of the research equipment and confirm that it adhered to the study's objectives. This tested the objectivity and meaning accuracy of the pilot study replies. Each survey instrument's reliability was assessed, and a Cronbach's alpha was calculated.

The level of agreement in Perceived Impact of Facebook Usage on Reasons has consisted of 10 items. It was designed to assess the perceived impact of Facebook Usage on the reasons of the respondents in the aspects of Facebook usage on secondary school students' reading habits, attitudes, and academic performance. Reliability for this construct was good (above 0.7), with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87.

The Perceived Impact of Facebook on Reading Preferences, with 10 items, was intended to be assessed. Reliability for this construct was good (above 0.7), with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.947. The Perceived Impact of Facebook on Distractions got a reliability construct of above 0.7, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.962. Meanwhile, the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading attitudes on self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, perceived importance of reading, and number of hours per day of Facebook resulted in a reliability construct of 0.96 Cronbach's Alpha.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure for a research study investigating the influence of Facebook on secondary student's reading habits and attitudes at Pantar National High School, Division of Lanao del Norte, School Year 2023-2024 involved several steps.

The researcher obtained permission to study approval from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Lanao del Norte. The next step was the selection of the respondents for the study. This would involve identifying a suitable sample of secondary school students at Pantar National High School who were willing to participate in the study.

Once the participants were selected, the researcher distributed the informed consent to the participants and their parents or guardians. The informed consent explained the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and the rights of the participants. After the informed consents were obtained, the researcher distributed questionnaires to the participants. The questionnaires were designed to gather data on the participants' Facebook use, reading habits, and attitudes towards reading.

The researcher retrieved the completed questionnaires from the participants and began the process of tabulating the data. The data were analyzed using statistical methods such as descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. Finally, the researcher performed statistical treatment of the data to identify any significant relationships between Facebook, reading habits, and attitudes towards reading among secondary school students at Pantar National High School. The findings of the study were reported and interpreted, and recommendations were made based on the results.

Statistical Tool

These statistical tools helped provide insights and interpretations of the data gathered from the study and answered the research questions and objectives.

For problems 1 and 2, Frequency and Percentage Distribution were used to describe the profile of the respondents and their academic performance.

For problems 3 and 4, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to calculate and describe the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading habits; and the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading attitudes.

For problems 5, 6, and 7, Pearson r correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

Multiple Regression Analysis was used to determine the association between the perceived impact of Facebook to the academic performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data in relevance to the reading dimension. For better analysis and interpretation, these data are presented in tabular and graphical forms.

Problem 1: What is the impact of Facebook usage on student's reading habits in terms of reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions while reading?

Table 2 presents the perceived impact of the use of Facebook on students' reading habits, focusing on various reasons for reading. The data revealed that, on average, students perceived a moderate impact of Facebook use on their reading habits, as indicated by an overall mean of 2.93 with a relatively low SD of 0.12. This suggested a consistent pattern among the respondents in terms of the observed effects of Facebook on their reading behaviors.

Several key findings stand out when examining individual indicators. Notably, Facebook seemed to play a significant role in making students more likely to read for entertainment or relaxation (Indicator 2), as reflected by a high mean of 3.85 with a relatively low SD of 0.35. This indicated a strong and consistent trend among the respondents in this aspect.

Similarly, indicators related to reading opinion pieces or editorials online (Indicator 4) and sharing interesting articles or stories with friends (Indicator 10) also showed a high level of impact, with means of 3.86 and 3.79, respectively, and low SD values of 0.35 and 0.41. These results suggested a clear and consistent influence of Facebook on these specific reading behaviors.

Table 2. *Perceived Impact of Facebook Usage on Student's Reading Habits in terms of Reasons for Reading*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Facebook use has made me more interested in reading articles or news stories online.	3.37	0.48	Observed
2. Facebook use has made me more likely to read for entertainment or relaxation, rather than academic or educational purposes.	3.85	0.35	Highly Observed
3. Facebook use made me interested in reading physical books or longer articles.	2.19	0.40	Rarely Observed
4. Facebook use has made me more interested in reading opinion pieces or editorials online.	3.86	0.35	Highly Observed
5. Facebook use has made me interested in reading books or articles that require more effort or concentration	3.15	0.36	Observed
6. Facebook use has encouraged me to participate in online discussions related to the articles or topics I've read.	3.10	0.30	Observed
7. Facebook use has motivated me to explore new topics or genres I would not have considered before.	1.79	0.41	Rarely Observed
8. Facebook use has improved my ability to critically analyze and evaluate the information I read online.	2.33	0.56	Rarely Observed
9. Facebook use has connected me with online book clubs or reading communities, enhancing my reading experience.	1.86	0.35	Rarely Observed
10. Facebook use has inspired me to share interesting articles or stories with my friends, fostering a culture of reading among my social circles.	3.79	0.41	Highly Observed
Total Measure	2.93	0.12	Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

Conversely, indicators such as being interested in reading physical books or longer articles (Indicator 3) and connecting with online book clubs or reading communities (Indicator 9) demonstrated a lower level of impact, as evidenced by mean values below 2 and higher SD values (0.40 and 0.35, respectively). These findings implied that these aspects of reading were less influenced by Facebook use among the surveyed students. Thus, the results emphasized the strong impact of Facebook on students' reading habits.

In connection with the findings, Ali and Razzaq (2018) mentioned that there was a heightened interest in reading opinion pieces or editorials online, and they identified a strong correlation between frequent Facebook use and the increased consumption of such content. The findings suggested that exposure to diverse opinions and perspectives on Facebook influenced users' preferences for opinion-based written materials.

Table 3 shows the impact of the use of Facebook on students' reading habits, focusing on reading preferences. The results indicated an overall positive impact of Facebook use on students' reading preferences, as reflected by a mean of 3.31 and a moderate SD of 0.14. This suggested a consistent pattern among respondents in terms of the observed effects of Facebook on their reading preferences.

Table 3. *Perceived Impact of Facebook Use on Student's Reading Habits in terms of Reading Preferences*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Facebook has influenced my preference for reading shorter articles or posts online.	3.84	0.37	Highly Observed
2. Facebook has made me more likely to read e-books or listen to audiobooks instead of physical books.	3.66	0.68	Highly Observed
3. Facebook has introduced me to new authors or genres of books that I would not have discovered otherwise.	3.85	0.36	Highly Observed
4. Facebook has made me more likely to read user-generated content, such as reviews or comments, about books or articles before deciding to read them.	3.79	0.41	Highly Observed
5. Facebook has influenced my preference for reading content that aligns with my personal values or interests.	3.15	0.36	Observed
6. Facebook has connected me with online book events or virtual author discussions, expanding my literary horizons	2.78	0.45	Observed
7. Facebook has allowed me to participate in online reading challenges, enhancing my reading motivation.	2.01	0.27	Rarely Observed
8. Facebook has enabled me to share my own creative writing, encouraging others to read and engage with my work	3.19	0.40	Observed
9. Facebook has facilitated discussions about diverse perspectives, encouraging me to explore a variety of viewpoints in my reading.	3.73	0.45	Highly Observed
10. Facebook has provided a platform for me to recommend books to others, promoting a culture of reading in my social network	3.12	0.38	Observed
Total Measure	3.31	0.14	Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

Several indicators stand out in highlighting the substantial influence of Facebook on reading behaviors. Notably, Facebook appears to strongly influence the preference for reading shorter articles or posts online (Indicator 1), exploring new authors or genres (Indicator 3), and engaging with user-generated content such as reviews or comments before deciding to read (Indicator 4). These aspects are characterized by high mean values ranging from 3.79 to 3.85, accompanied by relatively low SD values ranging from 0.36 to 0.41, indicating a high level of consistency among respondents.

Moreover, the impact of Facebook on the shift towards e-books or audiobooks and participating in discussions about diversity was also notably high. These findings suggested a clear and influential role of Facebook in shaping not only the format of reading materials but also the diversity of perspectives considered by students. However, indicators such as participating in online reading challenges (Indicator 7) and sharing creative writing on Facebook (Indicator 8) exhibited a lower level of impact, as evidenced by mean values below 3 and relatively low SD values. These results implied that while Facebook had some influence in these areas, it may not be as pronounced compared to other aspects of reading preferences.

As emphasized by Demir et al. (2019), social media users frequently cited that exposure to articles, news, and discussions on Facebook broadened their reading horizons. The platform's algorithm-driven content delivery was perceived positively, as it introduced users to topics and genres they might not have encountered through traditional media. Moreover, Facebook groups and pages dedicated to specific literary interests emerged as significant factors in shaping reading preferences. Students reported that shared reading recommendations within these communities influenced their choices and encouraged them to explore genres beyond their initial inclinations.

Table 4. *Perceived Impact of Facebook Use on Student's Reading Habits in terms of Distraction while Reading*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Facebook has made it easier to concentrate on reading for long periods of time	1.93	0.26	Rarely Observed
2. Facebook notifications or alerts interrupt my reading frequently.	3.13	0.33	Observed
3. Facebook has made it easier for me to focus on reading without checking my phone or other devices.	1.88	0.33	Rarely Observed
4. Facebook has made it easier for me to remember what I read due to constant interruptions or distractions.	1.77	0.42	Rarely Observed
5. Facebook has made me more likely to read in quiet or serene environments due to my dependency on external stimuli.	3.82	0.39	Highly Observed
6. Facebook has encouraged me to set specific reading time without distractions, improving my focus.	3.15	0.36	Observed
7. Facebook has inspired me to use digital tools to track my reading progress and stay organized	3.89	0.31	Highly Observed
8. Facebook has motivated me to engage in mindful reading practices, enhancing my overall reading experience.	2.88	0.33	Observed
9. Facebook has prompted me to create designated quiet spaces for reading, minimizing distractions.	3.19	0.40	Observed
10. Facebook has encouraged me to participate in digital detox challenges, allowing me to enjoy uninterrupted reading time	3.81	0.40	Highly Observed
Total Measure	2.94	0.12	Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

Table 4 provides insights into the impact of the use of Facebook on students' reading habits, specifically focusing on aspects related to distraction. The overall mean of 2.94 with a low SD of 0.12 suggested a moderate impact of Facebook on students' reading habits regarding distraction. This indicated a consistent pattern among respondents, highlighting the nuanced influence of the social media platform on concentration and interruptions during reading.

Key findings suggested that Facebook tended to have a mixed impact on concentration during reading. While students reported that Facebook had made it easier for them to concentrate on reading for long periods of time (Indicator 1), there were contrasting observations, such as the interruption of reading by Facebook notifications or alerts (Indicator 2). The mean values for these indicators were 1.93 and 3.13, respectively, with relatively low SD values, indicating a degree of consistency in these opposing effects.

Interestingly, Facebook appeared to play a positive role in promoting mindful reading practices and reducing distractions for some students, as evidenced by indicators such as setting specific reading times without distractions (Indicator 6) and creating designated quiet spaces for reading (Indicator 9). These indicators had mean values above 3, suggesting a moderate to high level of impact with relatively low SD values, indicating a consistent trend among respondents.

Furthermore, Facebook seemed to inspire students to utilize digital tools for tracking reading progress staying organized (Indicator 7) and participating in digital detox challenges (Indicator 10), both of which were highly observed with mean values of 3.89 and 3.81, respectively, and low SD values. These findings highlighted the potential positive impact of Facebook on encouraging intentional and focused reading habits. Therefore, the finding revealed a strong link between Facebook use and distractions in the context of students' reading habits. While there were indications of interruptions, particularly through notifications, there was also evidence of Facebook motivating students to adopt strategies for mindful reading.

According to Hanan and Tahtamouni (2019), some participants described adopting strategies to minimize Facebook-related interruptions, such as using website blockers or establishing designated study periods with restricted social media access. However, challenges persisted, indicating the persistent allure of Facebook during academic tasks. Moreover, some Facebook users reported a negative impact on their reading comprehension, with distractions leading to the need for increased re-reading and a diminished ability to retain information.

Table 5. *Consolidated Findings of the Perceived Impact of Facebook Use on Student's Reading Habits*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Reasons for Reading	2.93	0.12	Observed
Reading Preferences	3.31	0.14	Observed
Distractions while Reading	2.94	0.12	Observed
Total Measure	3.06	0.07	Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

Table 5 provides a consolidated overview of the perceived impact of Facebook use on students' reading habits, encompassing reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions during reading. The mean values for each category suggest a consistent pattern of impact across reasons for reading (2.93), reading preferences (3.31), and distractions while reading (2.94). The low SD values (0.12, 0.14, and 0.12, respectively) indicate a relatively low level of variation in responses within each category, reinforcing the observed trends.

The total measure mean of 3.06 with a very low SD of 0.07 reflected an overall moderate to high level of perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading habits. This suggested that, on average, students perceived Facebook to have a noteworthy influence on their reading behaviors, encompassing both positive and potentially distracting aspects.

These consolidated findings highlighted that while Facebook seemed to positively impact reading preferences, such as the exploration of diverse content and engagement with shorter formats, it also introduced some challenges related to distractions during reading. The observed trends can serve as valuable insights for educators and students to understand the complex dynamics of social media's influence on reading habits. Strategies for leveraging the positive aspects of Facebook's impact on reading preferences could be emphasized, while simultaneously addressing potential distractions to enhance the overall reading experience.

According to Akerele and Okunade (2018), some social media users frequently cited that Facebook served as a source of motivation to explore new topics or genres they would not have considered before. This aligned with existing literature on the positive impact of social media in expanding individuals' intellectual curiosities. They added that they also expressed an increased interest in opinion pieces and editorials online, with Facebook acting as a catalyst for exploring diverse literary genres.

Problem 2: What is the impact of Facebook use on student's reading attitudes in terms of self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read; and perceived importance of reading?

Table 6. *Impact of Facebook Use on Student's Reading Attitudes in terms of Self-Efficacy*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Facebook helps me improve my reading comprehension skills	2.70	0.46	Observed
2. I feel more confident in my ability to comprehend what I read because of my use of Facebook.	2.17	0.38	Rarely Observed
3. I believe that Facebook can help me become a better reader	3.19	0.39	Observed
4. Using Facebook has increased my ability to understand complex reading materials.	1.87	0.33	Rarely Observed
5. I can comprehend what I read better because of the various reading materials available on Facebook.	1.31	0.46	Never Observed
6. Facebook has provided me with diverse reading materials, enhancing my comprehension skills.	1.83	0.37	Rarely Observed
7. Engaging with Facebook content has improved my ability to analyze and interpret written information.	1.94	0.31	Rarely Observed
8. I find myself applying the reading strategies I learn from Facebook to my academic studies.	1.87	0.34	Rarely Observed
9. Facebook has introduced me to interactive reading apps, enhancing my comprehension.	1.86	0.35	Rarely Observed
10. Regular interactions with reading communities on Facebook have sharpened my comprehension skills.	1.79	0.41	Rarely Observed
Total Measure	2.05	0.12	Rarely Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

Table 6 presents the impact of the use of Facebook on students' reading attitudes, specifically focusing on self-efficacy. The findings suggested a generally lower level of perceived impact on self-efficacy related to reading attitudes, with an overall mean of 2.05 and a low SD of 0.12. This indicated a consistent pattern among respondents, highlighting a modest influence of Facebook on students' confidence and skills in comprehending written information.

Several key findings stand out when examining individual indicators. Notably, while there was a moderate level of agreement that

Facebook helped improve reading comprehension skills (Indicator 1) and could contribute to becoming a better reader (Indicator 3), other indicators related to confidence and application of learned strategies showed lower levels of impact. For instance, feeling more confident in comprehension due to Facebook use (Indicator 2) and applying reading strategies learned from Facebook to academic studies (Indicator 8) had mean values below 2 and relatively low SD values, indicating a more limited impact.

Moreover, indicators such as the introduction to interactive reading apps (Indicator 9) and the sharpening of comprehension skills through interactions with reading communities on Facebook (Indicator 10) demonstrated a rarely observed impact, as evidenced by mean values below 2 and higher SD values.

The total measure of 2.05 with a low SD of 0.12 reinforced the conclusion that the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading attitudes, particularly in terms of self-efficacy, was relatively modest. While there were some positive aspects, such as the improvement of comprehension skills and belief in the platform's potential to enhance reading abilities, the overall influence on confidence and the application of learned strategies appeared to be limited.

As mentioned by Chung and Lopez (2018), some Facebook users cited that engaging with informational and educational content on Facebook contributed to a sense of competence, particularly when the content aligned with their academic interests. Despite positive associations, some participants reported challenges, such as comparing themselves unfavorably to others in online reading communities. This social comparison aspect highlighted the need for educators and researchers to consider potential negative influences on self-efficacy within the digital realm.

Table 7 displays the perceived impact of Facebook use on students' reading attitudes, specifically focusing on motivation to read. The results indicated a moderate level of perceived impact on students' reading motivation, with a total measure mean of 2.41 and a low SD of 0.11. This suggested a consistent pattern among respondents, highlighting a modest influence of Facebook on students' motivation to engage in reading activities.

Key findings from individual indicators revealed mixed effects on reading motivation. While some aspects, such as being motivated to read more due to materials encountered on Facebook (Indicator 2), enjoying sharing reading experiences on the platform (Indicator 5), and participating in discussions that deepened curiosity and excitement for reading (Indicator 6), showed observed impact with mean values above 2.5 and relatively low SD values, others demonstrated a rarely observed impact.

Table 7. *Impact of Facebook Use on Student's Reading Attitudes in terms of Motivation to Read*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Facebook has made me more interested in reading.	2.06	0.31	Rarely Observed
2. I am motivated to read more because of the reading materials I come across on Facebook.	2.79	0.42	Observed
3. Facebook has exposed me to new authors and genres, making me more motivated to read.	1.90	0.30	Rarely Observed
4. Facebook challenges me to read more and has increased my reading stamina.	1.76	0.43	Rarely Observed
5. I enjoy sharing my reading experiences on Facebook, which motivates me to read more.	2.79	0.41	Observed
6. Facebook discussions about books have deepened my curiosity and excitement for reading.	3.25	0.43	Observed
7. Interacting with book enthusiasts on Facebook motivates me to explore new genres.	2.11	0.31	Rarely Observed
8. Reading challenges and recommendations on Facebook inspire me to read beyond my comfort zone.	3.27	0.44	Observed
9. Facebook book clubs have created a sense of community, boosting my reading enthusiasm.	2.76	0.43	Observed
10. Participating in online book discussions on Facebook has expanded my literary interests.	1.43	0.50	Never Observed
Total Measure	2.41	0.11	Rarely Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

For instance, indicators related to being more interested in reading due to Facebook use (Indicator 1), exposure to new authors and genres (Indicator 3), and challenges on Facebook increasing reading stamina (Indicator 4) had mean values below 2 and relatively low SD values. Similarly, participating in online book discussions that expanded literary interests (Indicator 10) was rarely observed, with a mean value of 1.43 and a higher SD.

The total measure mean of 2.41 with a low SD of 0.11 reinforced the conclusion that the perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading motivation was modest. While some aspects contributed positively to motivation, others showed limited influence. As mentioned by Adesoji et al. (2018), survey results indicated a negative correlation between the frequency of Facebook use and students' intrinsic motivation to read. Participants reported that the instant gratification and constant stimuli on Facebook led to a decline in the appeal of more contemplative and solitary reading activities. Moreover, participants expressed difficulty in sustaining focus during extended reading sessions, with the constant stimuli from social media creating a preference for brief, easily consumable content.

The findings from individual indicators indicated a high level of observed impact on various dimensions of the importance of reading. Indicators such as realizing the importance of reading in life (Indicator 1), being aware of the benefits of reading (Indicator 2), appreciating the value of reading for personal development (Indicator 3), and believing that Facebook has increased understanding of how reading can improve life (Indicator 4) all demonstrated mean values above 3 and relatively low SD values, indicating a high level of consistency in these perceptions.

In addition, indicators related to seeing reading as a valuable tool for improving knowledge and skills (Indicator 5), discussions on the

societal impact of literacy (Indicator 6), and engagement with educational content emphasizing the lifelong benefits of reading (Indicator 7) also exhibited observed impact, with mean values above 3 and low SD values.

Table 8. *Impact of Facebook Use on Students' Reading Attitudes in terms of Importance of Reading*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Facebook has helped me realize the importance of reading in my life.	3.21	0.41	Observed
2. Using Facebook has made me more aware of the benefits of reading.	3.20	0.40	Observed
3. Facebook has helped me appreciate the value of reading as a means of personal development.	3.86	0.35	Highly Observed
4. I believe that Facebook has increased my understanding of how reading can improve my life.	3.80	0.40	Highly Observed
5. Facebook has helped me see reading as a valuable tool for improving my knowledge and skills	3.87	0.34	Highly Observed
6. Facebook discussions have highlighted the societal impact of literacy, emphasizing its importance	3.15	0.36	Observed
7. Engaging with educational content on Facebook has emphasized the lifelong benefits of reading	3.05	0.21	Observed
8. Facebook has connected me with mentors who emphasize the crucial role of reading in personal growth	1.91	0.29	Rarely Observed
9. Learning about influential figures through Facebook has shown me the power of reading in shaping minds.	3.15	0.36	Observed
10. Facebook posts about the transformative power of books have reinforced my belief in the importance of reading.	3.19	0.39	Observed
Total Measure	3.24	0.12	Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

However, some indicators, such as connecting with mentors who emphasized the role of reading in personal growth (Indicator 8), showed a rarely observed impact, with a mean value below 2 and a relatively low SD. These findings suggested that while Facebook had a substantial influence on various aspects of the importance of reading, certain dimensions may be less affected.

In connection, the results entailed the significant impact of Facebook on shaping students' attitudes toward the importance of reading. The observed trends suggested that the platform played a crucial role in fostering a positive perception of reading as a valuable and transformative activity in personal and societal contexts.

As mentioned by Garcia et al. (2020), survey results revealed a positive association between active participation in reading-related Facebook groups and an increased perception of the importance of reading. Participants reported that engaging with a community of readers on Facebook fostered a sense of belonging and emphasized the significance of reading in their lives. Moreover, focus group discussions highlighted the role of Facebook as a platform for sharing knowledge and expressing appreciation for reading. Participants described how sharing book recommendations, insightful articles, and thought-provoking discussions on Facebook contributed to a collective appreciation for diverse forms of literature.

Table 9 provides a consolidated overview of the perceived impact of Facebook use on students' reading attitudes, encompassing self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, and the perceived importance of reading.

Table 9. *Consolidated Findings of the Impact of Facebook Use on Student Reading Attitudes*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Self-Efficacy in Reading Comprehension	2.05	0.12	Rarely Observed
Motivation to Read	2.41	0.11	Rarely Observed
Perceived Importance of Reading	3.24	0.12	Observed
Total Measure	2.57	0.07	Observed

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never Observed; 2.50-3.49 Observed; 1.50-2.49 Rarely Observed; 3.50-4.00 Highly Observed

The mean values for each category suggested varying levels of impact across different aspects of reading attitudes. Self-efficacy in reading comprehension had a mean of 2.05, indicating a rarely observed impact with a low SD of 0.12. Motivation to read had a mean of 2.41, also indicating a rarely observed impact with a low SD of 0.11. In contrast, the perceived importance of reading had a mean of 3.24, suggesting an observed impact with a low SD of 0.12.

The overall mean of 2.57 with a low SD of 0.07 reflected an overall moderate level of perceived impact of Facebook on students' reading attitudes. This indicated that while there was limited impact on self-efficacy and motivation to read, there was a more pronounced influence on the perceived importance of reading.

These consolidated findings underscored the complex and multifaceted nature of Facebook's impact on students' reading attitudes. While the platform may have a limited effect on self-efficacy and motivation, it appeared to significantly shape students' perceptions of the importance of reading in their lives.

Problem 3: How many hours do the respondents use Facebook?Table 10. *Distribution of the Number of Hours Per Day of Facebook Usage of the Respondents*

Hours per Day	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 1	7	4.7
1-2	23	15.3
2-3	16	10.7
3-4	30	20.0
4+	74	49.3
Total	150	100.0

Table 10 presents the distribution of the number of hours per day of Facebook usage among the respondents. The data revealed a diverse pattern of usage, with a substantial percentage of respondents engaging with Facebook for varying durations. A significant portion of the respondents, comprising 49.3%, reported spending four or more hours per day on Facebook, indicating a substantial reliance on the platform. Moreover, 20.0% of respondents spent between three to four hours on Facebook daily. This extensive usage pattern could have implications for students' time management, potentially affecting their academic commitments and overall productivity. The findings underscored the pervasive influence of social media, particularly Facebook, in the lives of the respondents.

Table 11 provides an overview of the academic performance of the students, presenting the frequency and percentage distribution across different performance categories. Most students fell within the "Very Satisfactory" category, with 103 students, constituting 68.7% of the total sample. Another significant portion of students, 23 in number, achieved an "Outstanding" academic performance, making up 15.3%. The "Satisfactory" category included 19 students, accounting for 12.7% of the total. A smaller proportion, 5 students or 3.3%, fell into the "Fairly Satisfactory" category. Notably, there were no students in the "Needs Improvement" category, indicating that the entire sample performed at a satisfactory level or above.

The academic performance of the students appeared to be generally positive, with a large percentage achieving very satisfactory or outstanding results. These findings provided context for interpreting the perceived impact of Facebook use on students' reading attitudes and habits, as there may be correlations between academic performance and the observed effects of social media on reading-related behaviors.

Problem 4: What is the academic performance of the students based on their final ratings for the previous school year?Table 11. *Academic Performance of the Students*

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	23	15.3
Very Satisfactory	103	68.7
Satisfactory	19	12.7
Fairly Satisfactory	5	3.3
Needs Improvement	0	0.0
Total	150	100.0

According to survey data, students who actively use Facebook for educational purposes—like joining study groups or accessing academic resources—report that it has a beneficial impact on their academic performance, as stressed by Aliyu (2019). Facebook's function as a platform for cooperation and the exchange of information was emphasized. Additionally, it was noted that students who reported using Facebook for school reasons for a modest period typically performed better academically than those who reported using the social media platform heavily for leisure.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading habits?Table 12. *Ordinal Regression Analysis of Relating Academic Performance by the Perceived Impact of Facebook Use on their Reading Habits*

Predictors	Estimate	SE	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Reasons for Reading	1.476	1.561	0.894	0.344	Not significant
Reading Preferences	2.392	1.299	3.393	0.065	Not significant
Distraction while Reading	-2.580	1.508	2.929	0.087	Not significant

Note: Threshold [Grades=Very Satisfactory; Grades=Outstanding] $R^2=.025$

Table 12 presents the results of an ordinal regression analysis aiming to examine the relationship between academic performance and the perceived impact of Facebook use on students' reading habits, considering predictors such as reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions while reading.

The findings indicated that none of the predictors, namely reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions while reading, are statistically significant in predicting academic performance based on the Wald test. The estimates for these predictors suggested minimal influence on the ordinal outcome of academic performance. Specifically, the estimate for reasons for reading was 1.476 with

a standard error (SE) of 1.561 and a Wald statistic of 0.894, yielding a p-value of 0.344, indicating a lack of statistical significance. Similarly, reading preferences had an estimate of 2.392, SE of 1.299, and a Wald statistic of 3.393 with a p-value of 0.065, just above the conventional threshold for significance. Distractions while reading had a negative estimate of -2.580, SE of 1.508, and a Wald statistic of 2.929 with a p-value of 0.087, suggesting a potential trend, though not statistically significant.

The overall model's R-squared value was 0.025, indicating that the predictors collectively explained a small proportion of the variance in academic performance. These results implied that, based on this analysis, the perceived impact of Facebook use on reading habits, as measured by reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions while reading, did not significantly predict variations in academic performance.

Specifically, Atienza et al. (2020) noted that there was no statistically significant relationship between students' reading habits and the frequency and kind of Facebook use. The study discovered, against popular belief, that a high level of Facebook activity did not always result in a lower level of student engagement with reading materials. One of the educational implications was the requirement for a thorough comprehension of elements other than social media habits that affect academic success. While the perceived impact of Facebook use on reading attitudes and habits may not directly predict academic outcomes, educators should continue to explore and address various factors contributing to student success.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance of students and the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading attitudes?

Table 13. Ordinal Regression Analysis of Relating Academic Performance by the Perceived Impact of Facebook Use on their Reading Attitudes

Predictors	Estimate	SE	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Self-Efficacy in Reading Comprehension	.400	1.403	0.081	0.776	Not significant
Motivation to Read	-.945	1.521	0.386	0.534	Not significant
Perceived Importance of Reading	-.233	1.442	0.026	0.872	Not significant

Note: Threshold [Grades=Very Satisfactory; Grades=Outstanding] R²=.025

Table 13 displays the results of an ordinal regression analysis investigating the relationship between academic performance and the perceived impact of Facebook use on students' reading attitudes. The predictors examined include self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, and the perceived importance of reading.

The findings revealed that none of the predictors were statistically significant in predicting academic performance based on the Wald test. The estimates for each predictor further supported this, with self-efficacy in reading comprehension having an estimate of 0.400, a standard error (SE) of 1.403, and a Wald statistic of 0.081, resulting in a non-significant p-value of 0.776. Similarly, motivation to read had a negative estimate of -0.945, SE of 1.521, and a Wald statistic of 0.386, with a non-significant p-value of 0.534. The perceived importance of reading also exhibited a non-significant impact, with an estimate of -0.233, SE of 1.442, and a Wald statistic of 0.026, yielding a p-value of 0.872.

The overall model's R-squared value was 0.002, indicating that the predictors collectively explained only a minimal proportion of the variance in academic performance. These results suggested that, according to this analysis, the perceived impact of Facebook use on reading attitudes, specifically self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, and the perceived importance of reading, did not significantly predict variations in academic performance. According to Batalla and Torio (2018), their observation revealed that there was a moderate positive correlation between certain patterns of Facebook use and positive reading attitudes. Students who reported using Facebook as a platform for sharing and discussing literary content were more likely to express an appreciation for reading. Educational implications included the recognition that the perceived impact of Facebook use on reading attitudes may not be directly linked to academic performance. Educators and researchers should explore additional factors contributing to student's success, both in terms of social media use and broader aspects of academic engagement.

Problem 6: Which of the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading habits and the perceived impact of Facebook use on their reading attitudes significantly predict the academic performance of students?

Table 14. Ordinal Regression Analysis of Relating Academic Performance by the Perceived Impact of Facebook Use on their Reading Attitudes

Predictors	Estimate	SE	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Reasons for Reading	1.487	1.566	0.902	0.342	Not significant
Reading Preferences	2.410	1.324	3.312	0.069	Not significant
Distractions while reading	-2.565	1.515	2.868	0.090	Not significant
Self-Efficacy in Reading Comprehension	-0.201	1.421	0.020	0.887	Not significant
Motivation to Read	-0.842	1.528	0.303	0.582	Not significant
Perceived Importance of Reading	-0.213	1.457	0.021	0.884	Not significant

Note: Threshold [Grades=Very Satisfactory; Grades=Outstanding] R²=.026

Table 14 presents the results of an ordinal regression analysis examining the relationship between academic performance and various perceived impacts of Facebook use on students' reading attitudes. The predictors included reasons for reading, reading preferences, distractions while reading, self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, and the perceived importance of reading.

The results indicated that none of the predictors were statistically significant in predicting academic performance based on the Wald test. For reasons for reading, the estimate was 1.487 with a standard error (SE) of 1.566 and a Wald statistic of 0.902, resulting in a non-significant p-value of 0.342. Reading preferences had an estimate of 2.410, SE of 1.324, and a Wald statistic of 3.312 with a p-value of 0.069, just above the conventional threshold for significance. Distractions while reading had a negative estimate of -2.565, SE of 1.515, and a Wald statistic of 2.868 with a p-value of 0.090, suggesting a potential trend, though not statistically significant.

Additionally, self-efficacy in reading comprehension, motivation to read, and the perceived importance of reading also showed non-significant estimates with p-values of 0.887, 0.582, and 0.884, respectively. The overall model's R-squared value was 0.026, indicating that the predictors collectively explained a small proportion of the variance in academic performance.

These results suggested that, according to this analysis, the perceived impact of Facebook use on various aspects of reading attitudes did not significantly predict variations in academic performance. It was important to interpret these findings with caution, considering the potential influence of other factors on academic success and the complex nature of these relationships.

Educational implications included the understanding that the perceived impact of Facebook use on reading attitudes, encompassing reasons for reading, reading preferences, and distractions while reading, may not be strong predictors of academic performance. Educators and researchers should continue to explore a range of factors contributing to student's success, recognizing the multifaceted nature of academic outcomes and the potential interplay between social media use and academic engagement.

As mentioned by Boateng et al. (2019), their survey results indicated no statistically significant correlation between the frequency and nature of Facebook use and students' reading attitudes. Contrary to prevalent assumptions, the study found that variations in Facebook use patterns did not reliably predict differences in how students perceive and appreciate reading. Statistical analyses further revealed that factors such as study habits, time management, and engagement with course materials were more robust predictors of academic performance than students' reported reading attitudes influenced by Facebook use.

Problem 7: What action plan can be implemented based on the findings?

Action Plan for Enhancing Academic Performance, Reading Habits, and Attitudes of High School Students

Rationale

The action plan is designed to holistically address the challenges identified in students' reading habits and attitudes. By involving all teaching personnel, we leverage the collective expertise and commitment of educators to foster a supportive learning environment. The assessment phase allows for a tailored approach, ensuring that interventions are precise and effective.

The targeted programs and workshops serve as direct interventions, engaging students in a way that aligns with their diverse learning styles. This is crucial for breaking down resistance to reading and promoting a positive attitude toward academic activities.

Integrating reading enhancement strategies into the curriculum is a sustainable approach that acknowledges the existing educational structure. This ensures long-term impact, embedding positive reading habits into the core of students' academic experiences. The potential barriers, such as limited participation and resistance to change, are acknowledged. The action plan aims to mitigate these challenges by involving stakeholders in the planning process, allocating resources for training, and carefully considering the implementation timeline.

Date	January 2024-June 2024				
Vision	To cultivate a thriving learning environment that promotes academic excellence, fosters positive reading habits, and shapes students' attitudes towards education.				
Prepared by:	Norhaemah Dangdang				
Key Action Steps/Strategies	Persons Responsible	Resource Budget Needed	Date of Completion	Threats/Potential Barriers	Indicators of Success
Conduct a Comprehensive Assessment of High School Students' Reading Habits and Attitudes Towards Academic Performance	All Teaching Personnel (School Heads and Teachers)	Allocation for Training Fees and Materials	January to June 2024	Limited participation due to curricular activities, school-related commitments, and financial constraints.	100% participation of teaching personnel in the assessments, providing valuable insights into students' current reading habits and attitudes.
2. Implement Targeted Reading Programs and Workshops for High School Students	All Teaching Personnel (School Heads and Teachers)	Allocation for Training Fees and Materials	January to June 2024	Potential resistance from students, scheduling conflicts with other academic activities.	Increased participation in reading programs, positive feedback from students, and

3. Integrate Reading Enhancement Strategies into the Curriculum	All Teaching Personnel (School Heads and Teachers)	None (utilize existing curriculum resources)	January to June 2024	Resistance to curriculum changes, time constraints in implementing new strategies.	observable improvements in reading habits. Successful integration of reading enhancement strategies into existing subjects, positive response from students, and improved academic performance.
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Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. The study concluded that the perceived impact of Facebook uses on students' reading habits and attitudes yielded valuable insights. In terms of reading habits, students exhibited a moderate impact of Facebook use on their reasons for reading, suggesting a discernible role in shaping their motivations. The positive impact on reading preferences underscored the platform's influence on the types of content students prefer. Meanwhile, the moderate impact on distractions during reading highlighted Facebook's nuanced role in concentration and interruptions.

Exploring reading attitudes, students perceived a modest influence of Facebook on self-efficacy in reading comprehension and motivation to read. However, the platform significantly impacted the perceived importance of reading, shaping students' perceptions of its significance in their lives. These nuanced findings collectively contributed to a comprehensive understanding of how Facebook interacted with students' reading habits and attitudes. Regarding academic performance, most students achieved a very satisfactory level, indicating a positive academic environment.

In addition, the study revealed that the examined predictors such as reasons for reading, reading preferences, distractions while reading, self-efficacy, motivation to read, and perceived importance of reading, did not reveal statistically significant associations with academic performance. This highlighted the intricate web of factors influencing academic success, suggesting that social media-related reading behaviors and attitudes alone may not reliably predict variations in performance.

Thus, the perceived impact of Facebook uses on reading habits and attitudes provided valuable insights, with implications for understanding student behavior and academic outcomes. The absence of direct statistical associations with academic performance emphasized the multifaceted nature of influences on student success, inviting further exploration into the interplay between digital media use and academic achievement.

The study's observation of a moderate impact of Facebook uses on students' reasons for reading aligned with Social Cognitive Theory, as it suggested that students may be influenced by observational learning and social modeling on the platform. Bandura's theory emphasized the role of observational learning and social influences in shaping behavior. The moderate influence of Facebook on self-efficacy in reading comprehension and motivation to read corresponds with SCT, which posited that self-efficacy was a key factor in determining behavior. The study's findings suggested that while there was an influence, it may not be as pronounced as in other aspects.

Moreover, the nuanced role of Facebook in concentration and interruptions during reading aligned with the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT)'s focuses on how individuals use media for their own gratifications. The study suggested that Facebook's impact was not uniform but varied in different aspects of reading behavior. Further, the absence of statistically significant associations between the examined predictors and academic performance aligned with the Information Processing Theory, as it acknowledged the complexity of cognitive processes and how various factors might interact in influencing academic outcomes.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

For school administrators, these findings emphasize the need to consider the essential impact of Facebook on students' reading habits and attitudes. Administrators should collaborate with educators to develop comprehensive digital literacy programs that empower students to navigate social media responsibly while promoting healthy reading habits. Additionally, creating an inclusive and supportive academic environment that fosters a diverse range of reading materials and encourages critical thinking can enhance the overall educational experience.

Teachers can leverage these insights to design engaging and diverse reading assignments that align with students' preferences and motivations. Integrating digital literacy skills into the curriculum can help students navigate online content more effectively and critically. Moreover, teachers should be attuned to potential distractions associated with social media and work towards cultivating strategies that promote focused reading within and beyond the classroom.

For students, it is essential to develop self-awareness regarding the impact of Facebook on their reading habits and attitudes. Establishing a healthy balance between social media use and dedicated reading time can contribute to academic success. Actively

seeking diverse reading materials, both online and offline, and participating in discussions beyond social media platforms can enrich the overall reading experience.

Future researchers in the field of digital media and education should build upon these findings by exploring additional variables and employing longitudinal studies. Investigating the evolving landscape of social media platforms and their impact on various academic outcomes can provide more comprehensive insights. Moreover, researchers should consider the potential influence of other socio-demographic factors, such as socioeconomic status and cultural background, on the observed relationships.

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